

Key Note LECTURE

KNL179. The DESIRED EU-funded Project. Converting CO₂ and H₂O into C₂₊ or CH₃OH under solar irradiation in a new concept reactor at room temperature

Michele Aresta^a, Angela Dibenedetto^b, Renata Solarska^c, Jiri Cejka^d, Bettina Munster^e, José Luis Galvez^f, Panayiotis Klitou^g

^aInnovative Catalysis for Carbon Recycling and Biopolymers-IC²R Ltd, Bari-IT, michele.aresta@ic2r.com; ^bInteruniversity Consortium on Chemical Reactivity and Catalysis-CIRCC, Bari-IT, angela.dibenedetto@uniba.it; ^cDepartment of Chemistry, University of Warsaw, Warsaw-PL, r.solarska@cent.uw.edu.pl; ^dCharles University, Prague-CZ, jiri.cejka@natur.cuni.cz; ^eAEE Intec, Graz-AT, b.muster@aee.at; ^fIMDEA Institute, Mostoles (Madrid)-ES, jose Luis.galvez@imdea.org; ^geBOS, Cyprus-CY, panayiotisk@ebos.com.cy

Michele Aresta

Solar fuels-SFs, produced *via solar driven CO₂ and water conversion* can contribute to drastically reducing global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and implement a *man-made carbon-cycle* complementing the natural-one, deploying the *circular economy* strategy. In particular, DESIRED does not target solar water-splitting, but a PCTE (“*Proton Coupled to Electron Transfer, H⁺ + e⁻ transfer*”) mechanism of reduction of CO₂, demonstrated in 1988 by the presenter (JCS Chem Comm, 1988, 7, 450-452) mimicking natural processes which do not use hydrogen for CO₂ reduction.

DESIRED seats in the EU-Mission “Innovation Green Powered Future”, aimed at developing sustainable fuels from non-biomass non-fossil sources, such as developing clean forms of storable chemical energy carriers, especially from direct use of sunlight, contributing to the defossilization of the energy and chemicals-fuels sector by 2050. DESIRED does not aim at the decarbonization of chemistry and energy but at the most effective use of carbon, without producing environmental harms.

SFs, in addition to their environmental benefits, enhance energy security (H₂ is not produced, stored, transported, or used) and provide opportunities for economic development across the globe. In fact, sunlight, CO₂, and water are ubiquitous and the DESIRED technology offers the opportunity of energy independence and renewable raw materials for the chemical industry to any country. Transitioning to new solar-based technologies can therefore greatly benefit developing economies and countries poor in fossil-C sources. DESIRED targets boosting the production of ‘*clean fuels from sunlight*’, which is today at a very early stage of technological deployment, through the development of a new concept reactor that can work in a dual mode as photo- and photoelectro-reactor.

The authors want to acknowledge the European Union for funding the research (European Horizon DESIRED, Grant Agreement No. 101083355).

